

Subclass of a certain Bazilevic functions associated with Caratheodory functions normalized by other than Unity with two radii

A. A. Yusuf *

Department of Mathematics, Federal University of Agriculture, Abeokuta.
 Ogun State, Nigeria. Orchid iD: [0000-0002-6322-0970](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6322-0970).

Received: 27 Feb 2021 • Accepted: 07 Apr 2021 • Published Online: 27 Apr 2021

Abstract: Following the approach in [6], we introduced a new subclass of Basilevic function associated with Caratheodory function other than unity define by a new operator denoted by $B_{\sigma,\gamma}^n(\lambda, \beta)$ and determine the radii of two disks in which the solution of certain integral equation involving a function $f \in B_{\sigma,\gamma}^n(\lambda, \beta)$ is in $f \in B_{\sigma,\gamma}^n(\lambda, \beta)$ and for which each function $f \in B_{\sigma,\gamma}^n(\lambda, \beta)$ is a $\sigma - n$ -spiral univalent.

Key words: Analytic and Univalent functions, integral and its inverse operator, salagean derivative and its antiderivative, radii problem.

1. Introduction

The increase rate of researches in the area of theory of geometric functions can be explained to be due to its wide range applications to many areas of study and hence, the growing needs for researches in the field to tackle different physical problems and as well as to show the interrelationship between analytic functions and other areas of mathematical applications.

One of the beautiful concepts of the field is the class of Bazilevic functions introduced in [2], defined by

$$f(z) = \left[\frac{\alpha}{1 + \zeta^2} \int_0^z [p(t) - i\zeta] t^{-(1 + \frac{i\alpha\zeta}{1 + \zeta^2})} g(t)^{\left(\frac{\alpha}{1 + \zeta^2}\right)} \right]^{\frac{1+i\zeta}{\alpha}}. \tag{1}$$

was discovered, where $p(z) = 1 + c_1z + c_2z^2 + \dots$ is a Caratheodory function and $g(z) = z + b_2z^2 + \dots$ is starlike, that is, $Rezg'(z)/g(z) > 0$. The parameters α and β are real number with $\alpha > 0$.

In [1], Abdulhalim, came up with the generalization of the classes of functions using the Salagean differential operator in [12] defined as D^n , $n \in \mathbb{N}$ as

$$D^n f(z) = D(D^{n-1} f(z)) = z(D^{n-1} f(z))'$$

with $D^0 f(z) = f(z)$, with the geometric expression

$$\frac{D^n f(z)^\alpha}{z^\alpha}, \quad n \in \mathbb{N} \tag{2}$$

having positive real parts in \mathbb{U} .

A further generalization was introduced in [10] that for a real number β , ($0 \leq \beta < 1$) such that

$$Re \left[\frac{D^n f(z)^\alpha}{\alpha^n z^\alpha} \right] > \beta, \quad z \in U. \quad (3)$$

and denoted the generalised class by $T_n^\alpha(\beta)$.

The works of Abdulhalim [1] have the starting point in the well know class of Bazilevic maps with some simplification done in [9, 11, 14, 15].

The concepts of the Bazilevic function was redefined in [2] together with a modified class of Caratheodory functions, which are normalized by other than unity and this gave a generalization of associated geometric conditions as defined below:

Definition 1.1. [2]. Let $\lambda = \alpha/(1 + i\zeta)$, the function $f(z)$ belong to the class $B(\lambda, g)$ if and only if

$$\frac{z(f(z)^\lambda)}{\eta z^{iu} g(z)^\eta} \in P_\lambda. \quad (4)$$

By taking $g(z) = z$ and using the salagean differential operator, we have the definition

Definition 1.2. [3]. The function $f(z)$ belong to the class $B_n(\lambda)$ if and only if

$$\frac{D^n(f(z)^\lambda)}{\eta \lambda^{n-1} z^\lambda} \in P_\lambda. \quad (5)$$

where P_λ is of the form $h(z) = 1 + \frac{\mu}{\eta} + c_1 z + c_2 z^2 + \dots$, involving the well known class of Caratheodory functions with a complex number $\lambda = \eta + i\mu$, $\mu \geq 0$ and $\eta > 0$, then $h(z)$ is said to belong to P_λ if and only if $h(0) = \frac{\lambda}{\eta} = 1 + i\frac{\mu}{\eta}$ and $Reh(z) > 0$.

Using the salagean differential operator $D^n f(z)$ and and inverse of integral operator $\mathcal{L}_{\sigma,\gamma} f(z) = \frac{(\lambda+\gamma)^{-\sigma} t^{\gamma-1}}{z^\gamma \Gamma-\sigma} \int_0^z (\log \frac{z}{t})^{-\sigma-1} f(t)^\lambda dt$ (see [4, 12]), on $f(z)^\lambda$, we have

$$D^n(\mathcal{L}_{\sigma,\gamma} f(z)^\lambda) = z^\lambda \lambda^n + \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \left(\frac{\lambda + \gamma + k - 1}{\lambda + \gamma} \right)^\sigma (\lambda + k - 1)^n A_k(\lambda) z^{\lambda+k-1}. \quad (6)$$

where A_k for $k = 2, 3, \dots$ depends on the coefficients a_k of $f(z)$ and the index λ .

We denote

$$\mathcal{L}_{\sigma,\gamma}(D^n f(z)^\lambda) = D^n(\mathcal{L}_{\sigma,\gamma} f(z)^\lambda) = L_{\sigma,\gamma}^n f(z)^\lambda. \quad (7)$$

$n \in N \cup \{0\}$, $\sigma > 0$, $\gamma > -1$.

Note that $L_{1,0}^n = D^{n+1} f(z)^\lambda$, $L_{1,0}^0 = D f(z)^\lambda = z f'(z)^\lambda$. If $\eta = 1, \mu = 0$, then $L_{1,0}^0 = z f'(z)$.

From the series expansions of the operator $\mathcal{L}_{\sigma,\gamma}$ on $f(z)^\lambda$, we have the recursive relation

$$z(\mathcal{L}_{\sigma,\gamma} f(z)^\lambda)' = (\lambda + \gamma) \mathcal{L}_{\sigma+1,\gamma} f(z)^\lambda - \gamma \mathcal{L}_{\sigma,\gamma} f(z)^\lambda. \quad (8)$$

Applying D^n on (8), we have

$$L_{\sigma,\gamma}^{n+1} f(z)^\lambda = (\lambda + \gamma) L_{\sigma+1,\gamma}^n f(z)^\lambda - \gamma L_{\sigma,\gamma}^n f(z)^\lambda. \quad (9)$$

Using the Salagean anti-derivative define as $I_n = I(I_{n-1}f(z)) = \int_0^z \frac{I_{n-1}f(t)}{t} dt$ and $\mathcal{J}_{\sigma,\gamma}f(z) = \frac{(\lambda+\gamma)^\sigma t^{\gamma-1}}{z^\gamma \Gamma_\sigma} \int_0^z (\log \frac{z}{t})^{\sigma-1} f(t) dt$. (see [4, 12]) on $f(z)^\lambda$.

Therefore

$$I_n(\mathcal{J}_{\sigma,\gamma}f(z)^\lambda) = \frac{z^\lambda}{\lambda^n} + \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \left(\frac{\lambda + \gamma}{\lambda + \gamma + k - 1} \right)^\sigma \frac{A_k(\lambda)}{(\lambda + k - 1)^n} z^{\lambda+k-1}. \quad (10)$$

We denote

$$I_n(\mathcal{J}_{\sigma,\gamma}f(z)^\lambda) = \mathcal{J}_{\sigma,\gamma}(I_n f(z)^\lambda) = J_{\sigma,\gamma}^n f(z)^\lambda. \quad (11)$$

It can be seen that

$$L_{\sigma,\gamma}^n(J_{\sigma,\gamma}^n f(z)^\lambda) = J_{\sigma,\lambda}^n(L_{\sigma,\gamma}^n f(z)^\lambda) = f(z)^\lambda. \quad (12)$$

Using the operator $L_{\sigma,\gamma}^n$, we introduce a new class defined as:

Definition 1.3. An analytic function $f \in A$ is said to belong to the class $B_{\sigma,\gamma}^n(\lambda)$ if and only if

$$\frac{L_{\sigma,\gamma}^n f(z)^\lambda}{\eta \lambda^{n-1} z^\lambda} \in P_\lambda(\beta). \quad (13)$$

and the integral representation is as follows

$$f(z) = \{ \eta \lambda^{n-1} [J_{\sigma,\gamma}^n z^\lambda h(z)] \}^{1/\lambda}.$$

This work was motivated by the work of Babalola in [6] and our objective is to determine the radii of two disks in which the solution of certain integral equation involving a function $f \in B_{\sigma,\gamma}^n(\lambda, \beta)$ is in $f \in B_{\sigma,\gamma}^n(\lambda, \beta)$ and for which each function $f \in B_{\sigma,\gamma}^n(\lambda, \beta)$ is a $\sigma - n$ -spiral univalent.

2. Preliminary Lemmas

Lemma 2.1. [7] Let $w(z) = z + b_1 z + b_2 z^2 + \dots$ be a unit-bound function, then

$$|w'(z)| \leq \frac{1 - |w(z)|^2}{1 - |z|^2} \quad (14)$$

strict inequality holds, unless $h(z) = e^{i\sigma} z$, for some real number σ .

Lemma 2.2. [13] Let $p \in P$. Then Then for any complex number λ

$$Re \frac{z p'}{\lambda} \geq \frac{-2r}{|\lambda(1-r^2)|} Rep(z). \quad (15)$$

Lemma 2.3. [3] Let $f \in A$, for any complex number ζ .

If for $z \in E$, $D^{n+1}f(z)^\zeta / D^n f(z)^\zeta$ is independent of n , then

$$\frac{D^{n+1}f(z)^\zeta}{D^n f(z)^\zeta} = \zeta \frac{D^{n+1}f(z)}{D^n f(z)}$$

Lemma 2.4. [6] Let $q \in P_\lambda$. Then

$$\left| \frac{zh'(z)}{h(z)} \right| \leq \frac{2(1-\beta)r}{1-r^2}. \quad (16)$$

Lemma 2.5. [6] Let $h \in P_\lambda$. Then

$$\frac{zh'(z)}{h(z)} \geq \frac{-2(1-\beta)r}{1-r^2}. \quad (17)$$

3. Main Results

Theorem 3.1. Let $f \in B_{\sigma,\gamma}^n(\lambda, \beta)$. Then the solution of the integral equation

$$f^\lambda(z) = \frac{\lambda+c}{z^c} \int_0^z t^{c-1} F^\lambda(t) dt \quad (18)$$

given by

$$F(z) = \left(\frac{(z^c f^\lambda(z))'}{(\lambda+c)z^{c-1}} \right) \quad (19)$$

is in $B_{\sigma,\gamma}^n(\lambda, \beta)$ provided $|z| < r_0(\lambda, c)$, where $r_0(\lambda, c)$ is defined as

$$r_0(\lambda, c) = \frac{\sqrt{1+|\lambda+1|^2}-1}{|\lambda+1|}. \quad (20)$$

Proof. Let

$$F(z) = \left(\frac{(z^c f^\lambda(z))'}{(\lambda+c)z^{c-1}} \right)^{1/\lambda} \quad (21)$$

then we have

$$(\lambda+c)F^\lambda(z) = z(f^\lambda(z))' + cf^\lambda(z)$$

so that

$$(\lambda+c) \frac{L_{\sigma,\gamma}^n F(z)^\lambda}{\eta \lambda^{n-1} z^\lambda} = c \frac{L_{\sigma,\gamma}^n f(z)^\lambda}{\eta \lambda^{n-1} z^\lambda} + \frac{L_{\sigma,\gamma}^{n+1} f(z)^\lambda}{\eta \lambda^{n-1} z^\lambda}$$

If $f \in B_{\sigma,\gamma}^n(\lambda, \beta)$, then there exist $p \in P$ such that

$$\frac{L_{\sigma,\gamma}^n f(z)^\lambda}{\eta \lambda^{n-1} z^\lambda} = \beta + (1-\beta)p(z) + \frac{i\mu}{\eta} \quad (22)$$

By differentiation and multiply by z , we obtain

$$L_{\sigma,\gamma}^{n+1} f(z)^\lambda = \eta \lambda^n z^\lambda \left[\beta + (1-\beta)p(z) + \frac{i\mu}{\eta} \right] + (1-\beta)\eta \lambda^{n-1} z^{\lambda+1} p'(z) \quad (23)$$

and

$$\frac{L_{\sigma,\gamma}^{n+1} f(z)^\lambda}{\eta \lambda^{n-1} z^\lambda} = \lambda \left[\beta + (1-\beta)p(z) + \frac{i\mu}{\eta} \right] + (1-\beta)z p'(z) \quad (24)$$

By substituting and simplification, we have

$$(\lambda + c) \frac{L_{\sigma, \gamma}^n F(z)^\lambda}{\eta \lambda^{n-1} z^\lambda} = (\lambda + c) \left[\beta + (1 - \beta)p(z) + \frac{i\mu}{\eta} \right] + (1 - \beta)z p'(z) \quad (25)$$

So that

$$\frac{L_{\sigma, \gamma}^n F(z)^\lambda}{\eta \lambda^{n-1} z^\lambda} = \beta + (1 - \beta) \left[p(z) + \frac{z p'(z)}{\lambda + c} \right] + \frac{i\mu}{\eta} \quad (26)$$

Therefore

$$\operatorname{Re} \frac{L_{\sigma, \gamma}^n F(z)^\lambda}{\eta \lambda^{n-1} z^\lambda} = \beta + \operatorname{Re} \left((1 - \beta) \left[p(z) + \frac{z p'(z)}{\lambda + c} \right] \right) \quad (27)$$

By lemma 2.3, we have

$$\operatorname{Re} \frac{L_{\sigma, \gamma}^n F(z)^\lambda}{\eta \lambda^{n-1} z^\lambda} - \beta \geq (1 - \beta) \left(1 - \frac{2r}{|\lambda + c|(1 - r^2)} \right) \operatorname{Re} p(z) \quad (28)$$

$$= (1 - \beta) \left(\frac{|\lambda + c|(1 - r^2) - |2r|}{|\lambda + c|(1 - r^2)} \right) \operatorname{Re} p(z) > 0 \quad (29)$$

provided $|z| < r_0(\lambda, c)$, where $|z| < r_0(\lambda, c)$ is the smallest positive root of $|\lambda + c|r^2 + 2r - |\lambda + c| = 0$. Hence

$$\frac{L_{\sigma, \gamma}^n F(z)^\lambda}{\eta \lambda^{n-1} z^\lambda} > \beta$$

in the subdisk $|z| < r_0(\lambda, c)$. □

Corollary 3.1. *If $\zeta = 0$, $\eta = \lambda = \alpha$, then $f \in B_{\sigma, \gamma}^n(\alpha, \beta)$ and the result is similar to that in [6].*

Corollary 3.2. *If $\beta = 0$ and $\lambda = \frac{\alpha}{1+i\zeta}$, then $B_{\sigma, \gamma}^n(\alpha, \zeta)$ and the result is similar to that in [6].*

Corollary 3.3. *If $\zeta = 0$, $n = 1$, $\sigma = 1$ and $\gamma = 0$, then $B_{1,0}^1(\alpha)$ and the result is similar to that in [6].*

Theorem 3.2. *Let $f \in B_{\sigma, \gamma}^n(\lambda, \beta)$. Then f is $\sigma - n$ -spiral univalent in the disk $|z| < r_0(\eta, \mu, \beta)$ where $r_0(\eta, \mu, \beta)$ is given by*

$$r < r_0(\eta, \mu, \beta) = \frac{1}{\eta - \beta|\lambda|} \left(\sqrt{(1 - \beta)^2 + (\eta - \beta|\lambda|)^2} - (1 - \beta) \right) \quad (30)$$

where $|\lambda| = \sqrt{\eta^2 + \mu^2}$ and $\sigma = \arctan \frac{\mu}{\eta}$. Which is the radius of the largest possible.

Proof. By definition, let

$$\frac{L_{\sigma, \gamma}^n f(z)^\lambda}{\eta \lambda^{n-1} z^\lambda} = h(z)$$

by some simple calculation, we have

$$L_{\sigma, \gamma}^{n+1} f(z)^\lambda = \eta \lambda^{n-1} z^\lambda \left(z h'(z) + \lambda h(z) \right)$$

and

$$\frac{L_{\sigma,\gamma}^{n+1}f(z)^\lambda}{L_{\sigma,\gamma}^n f(z)^\lambda} = \frac{zh'(z)}{h(z)} + \lambda$$

Since $\mathcal{L}_{0,\gamma}f(z)^\lambda = f(z)^\lambda$, we have

$$\frac{D^{n+1}f(z)^\zeta}{D^n f(z)^\zeta} > \beta \Rightarrow \frac{L_{1,\gamma}^{n+1}f(z)^\lambda}{L_{1,\gamma}^n f(z)^\lambda} > \beta \Rightarrow \frac{L_{2,\gamma}^{n+1}f(z)^\lambda}{L_{2,\gamma}^n f(z)^\lambda} > \beta \Rightarrow \dots$$

and so on for all $\sigma \in N$, where $L_{\sigma,\gamma}^{n+1}f(z) = D^{n+1}(\mathcal{L}_{\sigma,\gamma}f(z)^\lambda)$. By lemma 2.3, we have

$$\zeta \frac{D^{n+1}f(z)}{D^n f(z)} \Rightarrow \lambda \frac{L_{1,\gamma}^{n+1}f(z)}{L_{1,\gamma}^n f(z)} \Rightarrow \lambda \frac{L_{2,\gamma}^{n+1}f(z)}{L_{2,\gamma}^n f(z)} \Rightarrow \dots$$

and so on for all $\sigma \in N$, therefore

$$\lambda \frac{L_{\sigma,\gamma}^{n+1}f(z)}{L_{\sigma,\gamma}^n f(z)} = \frac{zh'(z)}{h(z)} + \lambda$$

Taking $\alpha = \tan^{-1}\frac{\mu}{\eta}$ and by Lemma 2.4, we have

$$Re \ e^{i\alpha} \frac{L_{\sigma,\gamma}^{n+1}f(z)}{L_{\sigma,\gamma}^n f(z)} = Re \left(\frac{\lambda}{|\lambda|} + \frac{zh'(z)}{|\lambda|h(z)} \right)$$

Using Lemma 2.5. we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} Re \ e^{i\alpha} \frac{L_{\sigma,\gamma}^{n+1}f(z)}{L_{\sigma,\gamma}^n f(z)} &\geq \frac{\eta}{|\lambda|} - \frac{-2(1-\beta)r}{(1-r^2)|\lambda|} \\ &= \frac{\eta(1-r^2) - 2(1-\beta)r}{(1-r^2)|\lambda|} > \beta. \end{aligned}$$

Provided

$$(\eta - \beta|\lambda|)r^2 + 2(1-\beta)r - (\eta - \beta|\lambda|)$$

Thus f is $\sigma - n$ -spiral univalent in the disk $|z| < r_0(\eta, \mu, \beta)$. □

Corollary 3.4. *If $\beta = 0$, then $f \in B_{\sigma,\gamma}^n(\lambda)$ and the result is similar to that in [6]*

Corollary 3.5. *If for $\lambda = \frac{\alpha}{1+i\zeta}, \beta = 0, n = 1$ then $f \in B_{\sigma,\gamma}^1(\alpha, \zeta)$ and the result is similar to that in [6].*

4. Conclusion

In this work we have been able to determine the radii of two disks in which the solution of certain integral equation involving a function $f \in B_{\sigma,\gamma}^n(\lambda, \beta)$ is in $f \in B_{\sigma,\gamma}^n(\lambda, \beta)$ and for which each function $f \in B_{\sigma,\gamma}^n(\lambda, \beta)$ is a $\sigma - n$ -spiral univalent of a subclass of Bazilevic function defined by composition of two operators, using the approach adopted in [6].

Acknowledgment

The author would like to thank the anonymous referee whose comments improved the original version of this manuscript.

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